

Supplementary Fig. 1: Regulating expression of *YPI1* by the use of a plasmid-borne doxycycline-regulatable system. Haploid *yip1Δ::KanMX* yeast cells containing an epitope-tagged version of the gene expressed under the control of the *tetO* promoter in the pCM182 plasmid (1), were grown in synthetic medium lacking Trp and, when appropriate, treated with 50 μg/mL doxycycline. Whole-cell extracts were prepared from culture samples taken at different time points. Forty micrograms of total protein were electrophoresed and the tagged proteins were detected by immunoblot using commercial anti-HA antibodies. Tagged Ypi1 results virtually undetectable after 9 h of doxycycline treatment.

1.- Gari et al. (1997) *Yeast* **13**, 837–848.